

Discovery and Access of Digital Film Archives: An Evaluative Study of Metadata Elements Used as Access Points

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ABSTRACT

In the era of digitization, audio-visual content is gaining much importance in the archives. The research focuses on discovery and access of digital film archives at a global level with an aim to ensure that digitized films are organized, discovered, utilized, and understood in the future. This poster presents the findings of eight digital archives with different domains, geographic origin, and purpose for wider use and adaptability. The study identified the metadata elements found across the access points studied for the films of the Oscar winning Indian filmmaker Satyajit Ray in the birth centenary year of 2021. These access points were further analyzed to see whether these help in promoting resource discovery by taking into consideration parameters such as overlapping access points and search options available. The authors end with a future scope to further investigate the availability and applicability of access points present in existing metadata schemas and uniformity at the item level.

KEYWORDS

Access points; Digital film archives; Metadata elements; Resource discovery; Information retrieval; Satyajit Ray

INTRODUCTION

The Indian film industry is the largest in the world with the maximum number of films being produced in more than 20 languages (Deloitte, 2016). Indian cinema was exhibited in more than 90 countries with the support of dynamic and current media, emerging as a global enterprise in the 20th century (Hafeez, 2016). Film archives aim at preserving the past happenings through audiovisual content which are an inferred representation of human endeavor (Brunow, 2017). Digital film archives nourish the storage, retrieval, and access to the films by digitizing them. Digital archives with multimedia content consist of a portion of the web where it is desired to have uniformity as per the content of the document.

Various studies have looked into the role of metadata in the access and discovery of digitized film archives (Atkinson et al., 2014, Wactlar, H & Christel, M 2002; Amato, G., Castelli, D., & Pisani, S.2000). Metadata should be self-sufficient to describe a resource with the enriched data elements without the user accessing the resource. In the scenario of outdated links found in digital objects, or if the digital file is not uploaded and made available to users, metadata provides the contextual information to a user to identify and locate the resource. Therefore, digital access points enable exact searches and data combinations for users. A thousand-hour digital video library is reduced to a terabyte or bigger mess of bits without metadata whereas with metadata, those thousand hours can become an important information source (Council on Library and Information Resources, 2002). The objective of this study is aimed at identifying the access points that exist in the selected digital film archives. We present our work in progress, by evaluating the content discovery through the access points across the selected film archives using noteworthy films by Indian filmmaker Satyajit Ray. Ray was one of the pioneers who brought Indian cinema to the world and was the first Indian to receive the Honorary Academy Award for his lifetime achievement.

RESEARCH DESIGN

To fulfill the objective of the study, a total of 8 digital film archives located across the world were selected as the sample. The criteria for selecting the sample archives were the presence of digitized films on the website and films by Satyajit Ray. The filmmaker Satyajit Ray was the first Indian to win an honorary Oscar in 1992. He was also chosen considering it was the centenary birth year of the filmmaker in 2021 causing a worldwide renewal in interest for seeking information and access to Ray's films (Majumdar, 2020; Tiwari, 2022). The research study was carried out using a mixed-method research methodology. Data collection included content analysis of relevant literature and a web-based survey. Content analysis was done to identify the film archives and web survey helped in the identification of the access points present on the selected digital film archives. Convenient sampling was used to proportionately represent both national and global digital archives. The selected sample digitized archives for the study were the British Film Institute (BFI), Yale Film Archive, Internet Movie Database (IMDb), IndianCine.ma, National Film Archive of India (NFAI), Library of Congress (LOC), OxDDB and the Internet Archive.

FINDINGS

Digital Film Archives Access Points

The right metadata elements make the archives easier to discover and access. These metadata elements which become the "access points" need to be made based on standards that everyone agrees on. Hence, the Online Public Access Catalog (OPAC) has emerged not just as an index to the whole collection of the library, but a high-quality catalog enables the user to efficiently find, identify, select, and obtain items from the collection.

Figure 1: Number of Access Points in the Archives

Analysis drawn from data presented in Figure 1, depicts the number of access points present in the archives. The access points were discovered by the method of web survey and further analyzed through the content analysis of the online catalogs. Internet Movie Database (IMDb) has the maximum number of 25 access points, BFI has 19, Yale Film Archive has 9 and Internet Archive has 6 access points respectively. LOC, NFAI, OxDB and Indiacine.ma have the least access points as shown in the figure.

Fig 2: No. of Common Access Points Present in the Archives

Data presented in Figure 2 illustrates the number and type of common access points present across the selected archives. The metadata element 'Author' which is also termed as creator or director and the metadata element 'Year' were the most common type of access points found in all the archives.

Figure 3: Availability of Search Options

Search options are a group of filters offered on the websites to help the user find the desired content quickly. A search option constitutes the various tiers of searching made available to the user i.e., Basic, Advanced and Expert

search. It was found that the choice of access points was made available in the Advanced and Expert tiers. Majority of the selected archives (LOC, OxDDB, Indiancine.ma, Internet Archive and Yale Film Archive) are providing two tier search options. Only two archives (IMDb and British Film Institute) are providing three tier search option. NFAI archive provides only one tier search option which is the Basic. The ease in retrieval of resources are the further implications that can be drawn through the availability of search options.

CONCLUSION

The research involves identifying the access points provided by the digital film archives to stimulate the usage of these materials by agreeing on description, metadata standards, indexing, etc. The study provides an analysis by retaining various checkpoints at each stage. The access points were mapped to the accuracy of the information retrieved. Some unique points found only on IMDb include color info, instant watch, filming locations, popularity, plot, runtime, sound mix, your ratings, filtering by adult titles. Future studies will explore the metadata schemas especially designed for films with the uniformity maintained at the item level and preparation of a skeletal framework for evaluating the search strategies for digitized film archives.

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